

5G-IANA is an EU funding project running from June 2021 to November 2024. The project aims at providing an open and enhanced experimentation platform that will provide access to 5G network resources, on top of which third party experimenters (i.e., SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. Taking a decisive step beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will engage in an extensive, multi-stakeholder cost-benefit analysis that will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as key advanced Automotive services enabler.

Use cases

5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven automotive-related use cases in two 5G testbeds.

- USE CASE 1: REMOTE DRIVING
- USE CASE 2: MANOEUVRES COORDINATION FOR AUTONOMOUS DRIVING
- USE CASE 3: VIRTUAL BUS TOUR
- USE CASE 4: AR CONTENT DELIVERY FOR VEHICULAR NETWORKS
- USE CASE 5: PARKING CIRCULATION & HIGH-RISK DRIVING HOTSPOT DETECTION
- USE CASE 6: NETWORK STATUS MONITORING
- USE CASE 7: SITUATIONAL AWARENESS IN CROSS BORDER ROAD TUNNEL ACCIDENTS

Testbeds

Ulm (Germany): operated by NOKIA

▶ ALL Use Cases will be demonstrated.

LTE/5G test network that covers an area of more the 100 km².

Ljubljana (Slovenia): operated by TELEKOM SLOVENIJE

▶ Use Case 7 "SACBT" will be demonstrated.

Dedicated 5G infrastructure for the purpose of the 5G-IANA project's demonstrations.

NOKIA

Ulm, Germany

TELEKOM SLOVENIJE

Ljubljana, Slovenia

Expected multi-level impact

5G-IANA aims to increase the uptake of 5G starting from the key Automotive industrial segment, where 5G/B5G business practical applications carry tremendous potential.

Significant benefits foreseen of 5G-IANA on the safety, environment and economy:

BY PROVIDING:

Real-time notifications about emergency cases on the road

BY SHARING:

kinematic information when overtaking

5G-IANA will:

PROVIDE INCREASE SAFETY

IMPROVE TRAFFIC FLOW BY PROVIDING REAL-TIME TRAFFIC DATA TO THE DRIVERS

Reduction in traffic volume

Emissions reduction by shortening the time-to-destination (and time for parking) for each driver

Drivers able to use alternative paths based on accurate data, thus increasing road utilization by 20%

A European project to provide an open 5G experimentation platform to enable the development, deployment and testing of Automotive related 5G applications

Main objectives

- To create new business opportunities and boost market for start-ups and SMEs with Automotive NetApps
- To increase road safety and reduce automobile carbon footprint by leveraging Connected and Automated Mobility using enhanced network performances
- To implement and trial Connected and Automated Driving relevant Use Cases to validate and assess the Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) suitability and functional improvements
- To provide accurate localization and low latency mission-critical applications
- To specify and provide the 5G-IANA AOEP
- To specify and implement a repository environment for NetApps and VNFs to ease the design and chaining of new automotive-related services

Consortium

5G-IANA Consortium comprises 16 partners within 8 EU Member States. The consortium counts on major research organisations actively involved in national and EU 5G projects, as well as telecom and IT manufacturers, and highly expertized SMEs.

5G INTELLIGENT AUTOMOTIVE NETWORK APPLICATIONS

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